
Review Article

Women Entrepreneurship and Its Practice within Nigeria's Microcosm

Shefiu Raheem

Department of Business Administration, School of Business and Entrepreneurship,
American University of Nigeria, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria
bestraheems@gmail.com

Abstract

The paper examines the status of the Women Entrepreneurs and their importance in birthing economic prosperity that is vitally needed to break vicious cycle of poverty. It also identifies the challenges faced by these women entrepreneurs, by reviewing various literatures and provides some suggestion or overcoming these obstacles. Women today have emerged as a key player in economic development of the nations. However this transformation of society is far from over and the women entrepreneurs not only face difficulties while starting up an enterprise but also during the running phase. Globally, they have become a key player in sustaining both social development and economic growth. Women in the last decades have made significant progress in obtaining responsible positions in the organizations. This paradigm shift is as a result of laws governing equal opportunities and equal pay; fair employment practices; changing societal attitudes towards women in the work place; and organizations' desire to place qualified women in managerial positions to project a favourable image. Many women are becoming more educated and the idea that a woman should stay at home, baby sit, cook, go to market, take care of the children and the home is no longer current. The number of women who are gainfully employed increases per day. Women entrepreneurs face a number of barriers in the quest of achieving their ambition. They face social barriers right in the beginning of the start - up phase followed by the financial barriers. Market and skill related barriers make it more difficult for them to begin their entrepreneurial ventures. Barriers created by their own fears and attitude towards taking decisions for starting the business is another factor for the dismal percentage of women - owned enterprises. However, amidst a lot of difficulties, they have proven their ability to manage not only small businesses but also convert them into highly successful large industries.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Success, Women Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurs, Challenges, MSME.*

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Introduction

Across the globe, women are starting businesses in record numbers. In the United States, for example, women own 9.1 million firms, or 38 percent of all U.S. companies. From 1987 to 1999, the number of woman-owned firms in the United States increased by 103 percent; employment by female companies rose 320 percent; and, even more astounding, sales grew by 436 percent. Female-owned businesses in the United States generate more than \$3.6 trillion in annual sales, and female entrepreneurs employ more people than the entire Fortune 500.

Although the United States may be the most reported example of the rise of female entrepreneurs within the industrialized world, woman-owned businesses are on the rise everywhere. In eastern Germany, women have created a third of the new enterprises since reunification in 1990, providing 1 million new jobs and contributing U.S. \$15 billion to the German gross national product. Female entrepreneurs in other transition economies, like Russia, Hungary, Romania, and Poland, are making a similar impact. In Latin America, according to the World Bank, fully half of all economic growth in the last decade throughout the region is attributable to the creativity and hard work of female entrepreneurs. In South Asia, women now outnumber men as business owners. And in Southeast Asia female owned businesses have been at the forefront of that region's economic turnaround since the "Asian flu" arrived in 1997.

In developing economies, studies suggest similar trends among the female entrepreneurs when compared to the developed countries. Amorós and Bosma (2013) report shows that about 41% of females established new businesses as opposed to 29% among the males in Nigeria and Zambia.

It has been estimated that 40% of Nigerian women are entrepreneurs. The highest rate of female entrepreneurs worldwide is in Sub Sahara (Mohammed et al., 2017). Also a recent survey by the BBC suggests that about 40% of Nigerian woman are entrepreneurs and this is higher than anywhere else in the world (BBC). With the rise in female entrepreneurship in Nigeria, a study of these businesses is timely, important and relevant.

The growth of female enterprises is evidently good for economies. The rise of female entrepreneurs also benefits societies and women themselves. Those who desire to see the conditions for women improve all over the world have discovered the incomparable value of nurturing and cultivating female entrepreneurship. The benefits derived when women start and operate their own businesses are truly remarkable: increased self-

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esteem, quality of life, and life expectancy as well as reduced infant mortality, incidences of AIDS and other diseases, and domestic violence.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To promote the concept of women entrepreneurship as a tool that could employed and also deployed to break the vicious cycle of poverty in Nigeria.
- To identify the challenges of women entrepreneurship in Nigeria.
- To mobilize the womenfolk for economic prosperity leveraging on women entrepreneurship.

Research Methodology

This paper adopted a qualitative research design which entailed a critical review of literature on the roles of women entrepreneurship in economic growth and development and it could be deployed effectively to emancipate the womenfolk from excruciating poverty as a result of their entrepreneurial failures. The study adopted a conceptual approach. The use of systematic literature review

DEMYSTIFYING WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

A woman entrepreneur refers to a woman who organizes and manages a business (Pandian et al., 2011). Women entrepreneurs provide incomes for their families, employment for those in their communities, and products and services that bring new value to the world around them." Women entrepreneurs are vital to the economic development, poverty and unemployment reduction of a nation. They have roles to play in the social, economic, and political life of any nation. Moore and Buttner (1997) defined women entrepreneurs as: "women who use their knowledge and resources to develop or create new business opportunities, who are actively involved in managing their businesses, own at least 50 per cent of the business and have been in operation for longer than a year".

Investing women's business performance is one of the most effective tools for increasing equality between women and men and promoting women in society. Investing in special programs for women can have a significant impact on the country's economic development. Targeted action not only can bridge the gap between men and women, but eliminate discriminatory aspects of economic and social policies, programs and practices preventing women from fully participating in the economy.

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Women entrepreneurs simply referred to women that participate in total entrepreneurial activities, they take the risks that are involved in combining resources together in a unique way so as to take advantage of the opportunity identified in their immediate environment through production of goods and services (Okafor & Mordi, 2010). Olumide (2012) defines woman entrepreneur as a female head of business who takes the initiative of launching a new venture. Moreover, women entrepreneurs accept the risk that is associated as well as the social responsibilities so as to effective change in their day to day activities. Women entrepreneurs are also referred to as females who are engaging in the business by addressing their knowledge, skills and creating their ideas.

WOMENS' ENTREPRENEURIAL TRAITS

Women in entrepreneurship possess dual characteristics (for instance, they are firstly women and secondly entrepreneurs). Therefore, it was stated in Okafor and Mardi (2010) (2010) that women entrepreneurs possess characteristics which include strength and internal locus of control, ability to think and reason fast and endure (Mayoux, 2001), adaptability, innovativeness/creativity (Schumpeter, 1934, Drucker, 1985), managerial skill, accountability and credit risk (Thomson, 2002). It was suggested by Lituchy & Reavley (2004) that some of the characteristics of women entrepreneurs are sense of control and flexibility, a high need for achievement and autonomy, self-confidence, risk taking. Redien-Collot (2009) included attributes such as orientation of opportunity, need for achievement and preference for innovation.

CONCEPT OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP.

Women entrepreneurship is a monetary activity that entails thinking about a business endeavor, starting it, put together and consolidate every one of the elements of creation, operate the venture and embrace the dangers and handle the financial vulnerability engaged with maintaining a business undertaking. Women entrepreneurship has crossed the phase of change and it is finally in flight, yet it has a long way to go before emerging as fruitful business. The importance of women entrepreneurship to families and economies is well documented. Women entrepreneurship is an especially important contributor to economic growth in low and middle income countries. Ganesamurthy (2007) characterizes women entrepreneurs as a certain, imaginative and innovative women fit for accomplishing self-financial freedom exclusively or in coordinated effort, produces work openings for other people however starting, building up and showing the venture to staying up with her own family and public activity. Women entrepreneurs all throughout the planet are significant supporters of the economy, as they are having an effect in the financial field. They contribute various thoughts and a lot of energy and capital assets to their networks, and produce occupations just as make extra work for providers and other side project business linkages.

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THE NEED OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Figure 1: The Need of Women Entrepreneurship Source: Garg and Agarwal (2017)

Women entrepreneurship has increased in the last two decades. It is still a significant source of unexploited economic potential (Figure 1). The current degree of women entrepreneurship is only the tip of the iceberg in terms of what women are actually capable of. It differs from its male counterpart in several vital ways and is, therefore, worthy of further study. Henry et al. (2005) have affirmed that women entrepreneurship is an under-researched area with huge economic potential, requiring special attention.

These are some of the special issues that make women entrepreneurship an interesting and important area in its own right:

- Women entrepreneurship is a recent phenomenon. Women have traditionally been excluded from entrepreneurship and their function has mainly been in the home (Roomi and Harrison, 2008). This is still the case in many countries around

the world and for the purposes of this study women in business can be treated as a minority group. The level of women's entrepreneurship varies from country to country but is always lower than that of men (Kelley et al., 2010).

- The traits seen in entrepreneurs tend to fit masculine gender-role stereotypes rather than feminine gender-role stereotypes (Gupta et al., 2009). Women have to break free of these stereotypes to become successful entrepreneurs. In fact, women who score highly on entrepreneurial intentions also score highly on male gender identification and display traits generally considered to be masculine (Gupta et al., 2009). Hence women entrepreneurs are a special case among entrepreneurs in general.
- Women-owned businesses may differ from male-owned businesses in several important respects. These include the importance placed on social relationships, the types of businesses they own and the sectors in which they are active (Sathiabama, 2010).
- Women-owned enterprises generally underperform compared to male-owned enterprises. Low returns on capital have been noted, for example (deMel et al., 2008). In transition economies female-owned businesses do not perform as well as male-owned businesses. In fact, many female-owned businesses may not be profitable at all. In Lithuania, for example, as many as 75% of women-owned enterprises were not profitable (Aidis et al., 2007). In Turkey, female-owned businesses are fewer in number and smaller than male-owned businesses (Bayraktaroglu and Kutanis, 2003). Even in industrialised countries such as the UK, where there may be fewer barriers to entrepreneurship, the failure rate for businesses is higher for women than it is for men (Brush et al., 2003).
- Organisational theories are rarely gender neutral. Many theories relating to organisations and entrepreneurship were developed by men, using exclusively male samples. They, therefore, may not reflect women's entrepreneurial behaviour. In particular, the characteristics of women entrepreneurs are measured using male instruments and constructs (Moore, 1990).
- The subject of women's entrepreneurship is under-studied. There are gaps in our knowledge of the subject, and focus is often one dimensional (Carter and Allen, 1997). In particular there is a lack of theory and models for women's entrepreneurship (Winn, 2004), and a dearth of research into its historical, cultural

and structural aspects (Lund, 1996). There is also very little analysis from explicitly feminist perspectives (Ahl, 2006).

THE WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP 'S TRACTION

Over the past two decades, women's participation in economic development using their labor force has increased. The entrance of women into occupational and self-employment ownership has become a prominent trend in the world (Butler, 2003). In the US, for example, over the past 15 years, women-owned companies have grown one and a half times as large as other small businesses and now account for about 30 percent of all businesses. Today, four out of every ten businesses (40 percent) in the US are held by women. Women entrepreneurs make up 8 percent of the total private sector workforce and 4.3 percent of total revenue.

Despite the participation of women entrepreneurs in economic growth and social welfare, women entrepreneurship around the world is along with challenges (Kelley et al., 2017). Of the 49 economies surveyed by GEM in 2018, only six countries have equal TEA rates between men and women, including two in East and South Asia (Indonesia and Thailand), one in Latin America (Panama), three in The Middle East and Africa (Qatar, Madagascar and Angola). Today, many women entrepreneurs who struggle with sustainability issues have been unable to amortize their costs due to unsuccessful businesses and, as a result, have increased unemployment and poverty rates (Franco et al., 2010).

Middle East and North Africa region of which Jordan is a part is one of the lowest in the world in terms of women total entrepreneurial activity (TEA). In 2017, female TEA was 11 percent in the Middle East and North Africa. In the same year, the participation rate of women entrepreneurs in North America was 12.8 percent, in Latin America and the Caribbean 16.7 percent, and in East Asia and the Pacific 12.7 percent

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN THE DEVELOPING WORLD

Throughout the world, woman-owned firms typically constitute between one-fourth and one-third of the business population. While women entrepreneurs in both developing countries and developed countries share many characteristics, many more women in the developing world remain illiterate – although not lacking in intelligence, experience, and wisdom – and live in poor rural communities. Nonetheless, women have always actively participated in their local economies. In Africa, for example, women produce 80 percent of the food. In Asia, they produce 60 percent and in Latin America 40 percent.

In many cases, women not only produce food but market it as well, giving them a well-developed knowledge of local markets and customers. The majority of the impoverished in the world are women and children. The tiny enterprises undertaken by some of these women enable them to improve the quality of life for themselves and their families. These micro-enterprises have begun to attract much attention. Charitable and nonprofit organizations working at the grassroots have found that investing in women offers the most effective means to improve health, nutrition, hygiene, and educational standards. The Foundation for International Community Assistance (FINCA) describes women as the “most dependable, productive, and creative members of impoverished societies.” As women in developing countries acquire competence and experience, and as the artificial barriers to their full participation in the economic life of their communities gradually fall, the integration of feminine values into the workplace should create a more humane and balanced work environment. Because of their unique leadership style, women-run enterprises generally provide a caring, cooperative work environment in which individual growth and development are fostered.

At the same time, women’s ways of leading are proving themselves particularly effective in today’s turbulent economic world.

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN NIGERIA

Women in traditional Nigerian culture are considered homemakers and custodians of family honour. Women entrepreneurs tend to have lower levels of financial capital than men entrepreneurs, raise smaller amounts of capital in both debt and equity, and rely on the internal source of financing (family, friend and personal savings) (Lincoln, 2012). In Nigeria, women-owned businesses are not economically developed compared to that of men (Ekpe et al., 2014). This is due to institutional barriers which do not allow women to fully take part in economic empowerment programmes (Ekpe et al., 2014). Women are considered to have strongly connected to the family, and most work of maintaining the house is assigned to them (Motilewa et al., 2015). The generalisation of 'gender' in Nigerian suggest that women are not supposed to engage in stressful and high risk-taking ventures. This has discouraged many Nigerian women from developing, running, and growing successful business ventures. Aladejebi (2020) observes that widespread bias about social discrimination is not the main barriers women entrepreneurs encounter in South-West Nigeria. She concluded that lack of adequate training, access to start-up capital, and poor family support (including spousal support) hampers the growth of women entrepreneurship in the country.

PERFORMANCE OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

It is worth noting that small businesses play a pivotal role in the economies of the world, and therefore, understanding why small businesses fail (or succeed) is critical to the stability of the global economy (Titus, 2008). Policymakers in most countries have been provoked by what they see as the potential for producing small businesses jobs. The high rate of failure of small businesses causes a serious waste of resources and is along with economic and human costs. The high rate of small business failure causes a serious waste of resources and consequently, increases economic and human costs. Accordingly, it is important to understand the reasons for the failure of new small businesses. Most women are involved in Micro Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (MSMES) which contribute more than 97% of all enterprises, 60% of the nation's GDP and a 97% of the total share of the employment (Ndubusi, 2004). The spectrum of women in entrepreneurship often ranges from home based businesses (HBB) to micro, small and medium enterprises (MSEs) (ILO, 2006). Okafor & Mordi, (2010) opined that women possess dual characteristic (For instance they are firstly women and secondly entrepreneurs). Women entrepreneurs possess characteristics which include adaptability, innovativeness/creativity, strength and internal locus of control (Annenkova, 2001), ability to think and reason fast and endure (Mayoux, 2001), managerial skill, accountability and credit risk.

EMPOWERING WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS.

Entrepreneurship is one of the best tactics within the strategic realm empowering women and upgrading their status. In mind of billions of the world's women, life is a complex web of constraints, obligations, and sacrifices, many of which are determined from the day of their birth. The caste or ethnic group into which a woman is born determines her status and her degree of freedom. Group identify is just one element of status. Patriarchal family structures continue to dictate much of the course of a woman's life. Many women in developing countries have few options for survival other than getting married and producing children.

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS' EMPOWERMENT LEVERAGING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY.

Use of new information and communication technologies such as the Internet is one of the most important ways to reach the global market. Women owners of SMEs can now use computers to exchange information on supply and demand, market prices, and micro-credit and to market traditional handicrafts, textiles, and agricultural products. Already throughout the developing world, the Internet is proving its enormous potential for competing in local markets, and in the global market as well. Information and communication technologies can also promote critical social goals by enabling women

and families in remote regions to receive critical health and education services, which they otherwise might not receive.

PROBLEMS FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

Women entrepreneurs generally across the globe are said to be confronted with the following problems:

- **Lack of Education:** Searching for opportunities, ability to examine and understanding them and building a successful business around this opportunity are the essential traits of an entrepreneur and to be able to do this, education is an important factor. It has been experienced that the female population in developed countries are more educated as compared to their counterparts in developing countries. In India, the situation is that the 56% of female population is literate with majority of them not even having education beyond school. This leads to a scenario where the women entrepreneurs are not adequately equipped to the latest developments in technology or market, let alone being aware about new business opportunities. Thus, women entrepreneurs run into a number of problems while setting up and operating their businesses due to this deficiency.
- **Social Barrier:** Gender discrimination, fear of reaction from the society, family responsibilities and commitments are some of the factors that combine together to make a social barrier for women to venture into entrepreneurship. Women in India are treated as subordinates and live as dependents to men and thus it is assumed that entrepreneurship is not the subject of women as it is a total preserve for men. The duties, responsibilities and obligations towards family is considered to be acting as a barrier for women to take up entrepreneurship. Various surveys show that this attitude is a result of pressures brought by the conservative thinking of a traditional society as the women are expected to prioritize delivery on family front as against any other activity. It is more visible and prominent in rural areas where the traditional role of women results into almost no or less time to be spared for business activities. The women are made to feel guilty in case there is any lapse towards family duties thus indicating the lack of family support and commitment towards the development of women in society. This also restricts a woman from setting up and running a business, visiting banks, attending entrepreneurship development training courses and seminars and conferences, attracting customers or looking for diversified suppliers.
- **Financial Problem:** The Financial problem of businesses is related to shortage of adequate finance, difficulties in obtaining credit from banks, Low risk-bearing

capacity, problem in capital for expansion, unaware about appropriate finance sources, lack of collateral, complex and lengthy loan procedures, etc. In India, women entrepreneurs always suffer from inadequate and inappropriate finance resources. They are unable to acquire finance from external sources such as formal financial institutions due to low creditworthiness and absence of accurate collateral as women have very less property and bank balance in their name. Research done by Robert in non-OECD and developing economies reveals that 59 percent of the respondents have mentioned financial problem as crucial problem followed by 41% having difficulty in obtaining a loan (Sandhu et al., 2012) discussed in his research that bank official takes a final decision on a loan application of women entrepreneurs when female owners provide collateral and have given a letter of guarantee from blood relation or husband or a head of the village for setting up enterprises. It is normally believed that women being feminist gender have low risk taking ability. Thus, women entrepreneurs start a business with a very low level of capitalisation and low level of debt finance and do not use much of private equity for their business sustainability due to unfavourable internal and external conditions of them, this financial exclusion is due to voluntary and involuntary reasons. Women entrepreneurs have voluntarily excluded from banking services due to lack of literacy as well as complex and lengthy procedures of bank loans. On the other hand, involuntary exclusion from financial services is happening as banks are not interested to provide loan facilities due to high interest rate, low level of credit worthiness, absence of past credit history, low level of credit bearing capacity and unhealthy relationship with banks while availing bank credit. In addition, women entrepreneurs are not aware of financial assistance i.e. subsidies, incentives, tax relief etc. provided by the financial institutions and government which result into business failure. This results into women becoming more dependent on her small savings and loan from family and friends for their day to day operations which is not sufficient for business sustainability.

- **Personal Barriers:** Personal barrier are related to women entrepreneurs in their personal capacity or their own mental blocks that stops them from taking risks and starting businesses. Also, general assumption about women characteristics in the society like lack of entrepreneurial aptitude, lack of self - confidence and fear of failure, problem of gaining confidence and support from other businesses, lack of involvement with business colleagues etc. acts as personal barriers.

- **Self - confidence and fear of failure** - The general assumption is that globally, men are much optimistic and confident than women in terms of their business opportunities and running a business. The lack of self - confidence is the one of the crucial problems to women who want to perform entrepreneurial activity into micro and small enterprises. It is considered that the self- confidence level in women is less as compared to women in general. However, the level of confidence varies from person to person and situation to situation and hence this may not hold true when it comes to self-confidence in handling entrepreneurial activities. Female owners though have a fear of failure and this has been related to the social and economic challenges faced by them as per a research carried by Halkias et al., 2011. Some researches show that women may be able to come over this barrier and enhance their level of self - confidence by participating in various entrepreneurial training programmes, workshops and seminar conducted by government and government departments.
- **Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude** - Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude and behaviour is one of the personal barriers in the way of start and grow of any business activities. Generally, upbringing of women is not as well as men with respect to business understanding and thus, they have no entrepreneurial bent of mind even after participating in a number of entrepreneurship development programmes and training, workshops, seminar etc. Only some of the women start and runs the business after improving on their pessimistic attitude towards entrepreneurship or compulsion and increase risk bearing capacities and calibre.
- **Market Related Barrier:** Marketing is an organizational function that creates, communicates and delivers value to customers. However, strong competition, weak marketing network, poor sales strategies, delays in payment by clients, lesser marketing experience and rapid change in demand and technology are the factors that pressure the women enterprises to respond quickly to changing market scenario. In general, Women - owned micro, small and medium enterprises have been surviving under stiff competition from establish firms and male entrepreneurs in term of cost, quality, standards and meeting the dynamic demand of customers. Also, male entrepreneurs have much experience, knowledge of the market and adopt new technology in their production. But as women start their business with small saving and small investment thus, they do not have adequate money to spend the advertisement of their products and services. Thus, females entrepreneurs have been doing limited marketing activities, mostly depends on middle men i.e. distributors, retailer etc. who try to take a major part of margin resulting into less profit for the firm. This results into

less money for expansion and upgrading of technology. Inferior and inefficient technology produces low quality and costlier products making them uncompetitive in the market which is one of the major reasons for failure of the business. Networking in their own social network is another way to market products as this is less costly and an emotional touch is there. Also, it would enable them to have access to information and make it easier for the women entrepreneur to easily access customers, suppliers and financial resources from close connections rather than business co-operators or colleagues.

- **Skill Related Barrier:** Higher technical and general managerial skills are the quality which an entrepreneur obtains during his or her life during the course of entrepreneurial training and education received and prior industrial and managerial experience. This enables the entrepreneur to discover and exploit better career or business opportunities. However, women entrepreneurs in India and several other developing countries have been facing barriers related to skill i.e. lack of prior managerial and industrial experience, lack of technical and general skill, inadequate and timely entrepreneurial training and education, etc.. These barriers create obstacles in the growth and development of women - owned enterprises. Also, women entrepreneurs in India do not having sufficient time to enhance their skill related ability by attending entrepreneurial programmes due to several social barriers. Government and Ministry of MSME have taken several initiatives by conducting Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs), Entrepreneurship cum Skill Development Programmes (ESDPs) and Training of Trainers (ToTs) programmes in the areas of Entrepreneurship and Skill Development. During the year 2015-16, 4,818 and 27, 557 women had trained by NI- MSME and NSIC respectively through various training programmes. The inability to attend such training programmes and workshops due to social barriers limits the managerial capabilities of the women entrepreneurs. The women entrepreneurs are less efficient when it comes to executing various functions like planning, marketing, motivation of work force, controlling and coordinating between various business functions, etc.
- **Operational Barriers:** Women entrepreneurs are given a similar type of training by the EDPs, irrespective of the firm being a start-up or old. This results into severe lack of knowledge for running a business. Second - generation women entrepreneurs already have an exposure to business and therefore, need guidance and advisory to manage the unpredictable situation, which may arise, due to unexpected events, economic or political. One such example is of demonetisation

where the cash was not at disposal and hence the purchasing power of individuals has dropped. Also, a number of agencies have business development programmes for startup phase, but once the business is established, the women entrepreneurs are left on their own to compete in an environment that does not provide a level playing field. The women entrepreneurs severely lack on the experience of operating a business and hence counseling, guidance, mentoring and advisory services can help them overcome the barriers faced by them while operating a business that was set-up with a lot of hard work and make it successful.

Other barriers: Some of the other barriers caused by the barriers mentioned above or due to a combination of above barriers are mentioned below.

- Obsolescence of Technology / Technological Development Problems
- Legal Formalities
- Shortage of Raw Materials
- Lack of Government Support/ Cumbersome Government Procedures
- Lack of Availability of Motivational Factors
- Direct and Indirect Tax-related Issues
- Location of Business
- High Turnover of Staff
- Lack of Awareness about Government Schemes and Policies.

In spite, of so many hurdles, the women today are venturing into any and every field including trading and manufacturing. Any nation with a large population of females, like India, cannot ignore the hidden potential and hence, much - needed support both from society and the government authorities is required. This would help the nation's economy to grow at much faster pace and contribute to reducing a major issue faced by the nation, unemployment.

Conclusion

The participation of women in the entrepreneurial activity makes them not only self - confident but also self - dependant. Thus, it provides them an opportunity of not only contributing to the economic development of the nation, but also enables them to give a better life to their family.

Today's women have ventured into manufacturing, trading and service sector from the earlier days where they were limited only to the domestic jobs. The women make up for

almost 50% of the population in Nigeria, however, only few firms in the MSME sector are owned by them. Supporting, the women entrepreneurs can provide a much - needed boost to the economy by creating new employment opportunities.

Women entrepreneurs face a number of barriers in the quest of achieving their ambition. They face social barriers right in the beginning of the start - up phase followed by the financial barriers. Market and skill related barriers make it more difficult for them to begin their entrepreneurial ventures. Barriers created by their own fears and attitude towards taking decisions for starting the business is another factor for the dismal percentage of women - owned enterprises. However, amidst a lot of difficulties, they have proven their ability to manage not only small businesses but also convert them into highly successful large industries.

A proper environment with support from society, primarily their own family, and government can solve many of the issues and as such, government has rolled out several initiatives and schemes to help women entrepreneurs to overcome these barriers. There are numerous schemes, wherein women receive additional benefits/concessions/assistance .Also, with higher education and increasing literacy rates, the view of the society is also changing towards venturing of women into entrepreneurial activities. In the constantly changing scenario, the government should not only spread awareness at a large scale about various initiatives for women entrepreneurs but also setup dedicated centres for helping women entrepreneurs. Also, a single window setup for women entrepreneurs staffed with well informed and skilled personnel could help the women entrepreneurs to manage the cumbersome government procedures, manage tax related issues and complete legal formalities. Designing training programmes and workshops, more relevant to today's scenario along with programmes addressing needs of the women entrepreneurs at various stages of the firm's life cycle would immensely help them by equipping them with skills and knowledge required to create a successful firm.

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